

THE SOCIAL SIGNIFICANCE OF DEVELOPING MANAGEMENT CULTURE OF FUTURE EDUCATORS

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Annotation. *Ensuring the compliance of preschool educational organizations with the requirements of a developed society requires the creation of a flexible system of pedagogical management. Taking into account that management culture is an integral part of professional pedagogical culture, the article examines the social importance of developing management culture of future educators.*

Key words: *preschool education organizations, pedagogical management, management culture, professional pedagogical culture, future educator.*

The growing interest of the future preschool educator in the culture of management is connected with the growing requirements for the level of general cultural and professional preparation of graduates of pedagogical higher educational institutions. The analysis of the results of the study of management culture of preschool educators showed that the results in this area are not satisfactory. This is due to the fact that for many years the activities of educators in preschool educational organizations in managing the educational process have been reduced to the implementation of official instructions. It was found that there are no different positions and different pedagogical approaches to the management problems of preschool educational organizations.

In modern conditions, the possibility of choosing programs, methods, tools and forms of the pedagogical process, on the one hand, opens the way for the creative self-realization of a preschool education specialist, on the other hand, it sets special requirements. That is, it is important to develop the level of professional culture of managing the pedagogical process of a preschool educational institution.

In the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 9, 2017 No. PD-3261 "On measures to radically improve the system of preschool education", preschool education capable of solving the issues of raising and comprehensive development of children at a professional level. The task of training pedagogues-educators of lim organizations is defined [1].

The issues of training future educators have been reflected in a number of studies.

According to G.N.Ibragimova, the process of preparing future preschool education specialists for innovative professional activities is carried out in higher educational institutions of pedagogy. Currently, the state and society are putting new demands on the process of training specialists in the field of preschool education [4].

According to the research analysis, professional training should be built in the direction of transferring the future educator from an objective state to a subjective state, that is, to a state of active professional self-education. At the same time, the formation of a subjective state is the emergence of confidence in the self-worth of the pedagogical profession and pedagogical activity. A motivational and valuable attitude towards them is an aspect and motive of professional self-improvement. Therefore, the formed pedagogical consciousness that correctly reflects reality and the dialectical way of thinking of the pedagogue represent his readiness for the relationship [21, 20].

According to Z.S.Teshabaeva, as a result of the formation of professional motivation in future teachers-pedagogues, professional competence also develops. In order to ensure the interdependence between them, in the process of higher education, it is necessary to increase the motivation of the future educator to a high level of confidence in the success of his work. Professional readiness is characterized by objective and subjective, creative-individual components of direct activity organization. Implementation of innovative technologies of education in the process of higher education to prepare future educators for professional activities; a high sense of social responsibility; develop skills and abilities to manage emotions; ability to quickly adapt to changes in society; to be prepared for various unexpected situations in the future; activation of different forms of thinking and creative abilities; it is desirable to develop the ability to cooperate with colleagues and parents [6].

In his research, B.K.Rakhimov studied the professional and cultural relations of future educators and educators. According to him: "Professional cultural relations serve as the main means of achieving effective, positive interpersonal solutions and serve to improve personal activity". [5]

A number of researches have been conducted on the pedagogical activity of the teacher. For example, it has been studied that the organization of cooperative activities of a child and a pedagogue-educator in mutual relations should be aimed at achieving the following goals:

- 1) the pedagogue-educator demonstrates an example of the optimal interaction of one person with another person in which a humanitarian-personal approach is implemented;
- 2) to demonstrate methods of communication with objects of reality that provide emotional bright, practical interaction;
- 3) teaching children communicative skills based on understanding the needs of others;
- 4) indirect teaching to dialogue, question-and-answer speech, to listen to another person, to be influenced by his words;
- 5) development of observation, formation of understanding of cause-and-effect relationships around [19].

In the conditions of the model of person-oriented interaction between the teacher and the children, training should be conducted in a design procedure that provides for the pedagogue's independent analysis of the situation, the choice of child-oriented teaching strategies, and the implementation of appropriate leadership. When designing situations, the motivation for acquiring knowledge should be the personal needs of the child, not human demands. From this it follows that developmental education is characterized by the child's independent search for solving various problems, which serves as a means of personal development, and conscious acquisition of knowledge [12, 7].

During training, mutual relations should be built on the basis of cooperation. Organization of cooperative activities with children ensures children's readiness for interaction. After a certain time, the functions of the pedagogue-educator and the level of independence of the children change, but the activity is maintained on the basis of cooperation. In the second stage, the teacher and the children work together in the middle group. In the third stage, children's independence grows [23].

Therefore, the effective organization of the pedagogical process in preschool educational organizations is based on pedagogical interaction.

Pedagogical interaction as a whole system consists of value-oriented components (pedagogical attitude, value orientations, norms, social perception, empathy, pedagogical orientation, personal qualities) and operational-communicative components (motivational value orientation includes pedagogic dialogue) [26].

Management is used in education in two different senses: management of the cognitive process, management of the entire educational process.

Problems of management of social and educational systems are studied by several experts.

According to U.Inoyatov, it differs according to the level and directions of management of the educational system. Including: 1) according to level - internal management of state, inter-branch, network, local and general education schools; 2) according to directions - organizational, systematic, meaningful, from the point of view of personnel issues and methodical [15].

According to R.Djuraev, "monitoring is the collection of information in order to provide the management of the educational system with information that allows drawing reasonable conclusions about the educational system or its individual elements, evaluating and analyzing its condition at any time work, processing, storage and distribution" [3].

M.Akhmedov "Quality assurance according to modern approaches of management is carried out in the sequence of: goal setting, planning, selection of methods and tools, monitoring and evaluation, analysis and correction. Without effective monitoring and evaluation, which is the main link of this sequence, there is no possibility to effectively manage the quality of the educational process and the entire educational system. In our opinion, in order to ensure quality in the institution, management subjects need constant reliable information" [2].

According to M.Meskon, M.Albert, F.Khedouri, the quality of management determines the results of the organization's activities and the selection of ways and means of achieving them. A well-organized and harmonious team is necessary to effectively solve the tasks facing the organization. In this, each of its members knows his job and performs it, works in harmony, without interruptions and solves most of the problems without conflicts, is interested in the final results [22].

The theoretical foundations of management as a specific professional activity were considered by foreign authors M. Albert [22], F.Khedouri [22] and others. Yu.A.Konarzhovsky [18] studied the characteristics of the professional activity of the heads of educational institutions and the determination of the factors affecting the effectiveness of the management of the pedagogical process.

Foreign scientists F.Taylor and F.Gilbert were the first to develop the concept of scientific management, based on scientific methods and technological standards, the principles of selecting (recruiting) specialists taking into account their abilities, their appropriate level of education and development. ensuring psychological compatibility of specialists with employers, cooperation and cooperation, rational use of specialists' work and means of production [27].

Scientists are also conducting research in the field of determining the functions of pedagogical management [25], developing approaches to the organizational structure of management, revealing the psychological mechanisms of leadership, forming professional and social partnerships, management and self-management, research in the field of pedagogical technologies, training issues of organizing the interaction of process subjects [10] were studied.

- The development of strategic management ideas is reflected in the scientific works of L.Zaysev [14].

- Taking into account that management culture is an integral part of professional pedagogical culture, the works devoted to the problems of professional training of specialists of preschool educational organizations were studied.

- The modern general theoretical approach to studying the formation of the teacher's professional-pedagogical, including management culture is defined in the works of O.A. Abdullina [8], I.A. Kolesnikova [17], and others.

- The problem of relations between general and professional pedagogical culture is reflected in a number of works: philosophical (P.S. Gurevich [13], M.S. Kagan [16], etc.); psychological (S.L. Rubinstein [24] and others).

- Social and psychological aspects of professional pedagogical culture were studied by E. Fromm [28].

- In the psychological-pedagogical literature devoted to the problems of training preschool education organizers-pedagogues, there are important studies related to the organizational-pedagogical activity of the head of a preschool educational institution [9], [11].

- Thus, in the process of theoretical research, it was found that scientists consider various aspects of the management activity of educators, but there are not enough studies directly devoted to the development of the management culture of a future specialist in preschool education.

- During the modernization of the education system, a number of contradictions that arise in the management of preschool educational organizations were identified:

- socio-economic changes, changed conditions of professional activity in pedagogical management in various pre-school educational organizations and insufficient development of the management culture of educators,

- insufficient development of the theoretical and methodological foundations for creating pedagogical conditions for the development of management culture of future preschool educators with the accumulated theoretical and practical experience of managing socio-pedagogical systems.

- In conclusion, the following can be noted:

- it is represented by the integral unity of the formation of the main components of the management culture of future teachers: axiological, epistemological and technological components;

- the stages of development of management culture of future educators are considered as a process (pedagogical - guiding, theoretical - analytical and professional - creative), which implies a consistent complication of goals, content, and tools.

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